

Effect of Buckypaper on the Properties of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Hybrid Composites

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ABSTRACT

A novel nanocomposite laminate was fabricated by sandwiching carbon nanotube films (buckypapers) between commercial carbon fiber (CF) prepregs through vacuum-bag processing (Figure 1). The effect of buckypaper on the damping factor, moisture resistance, interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and fracture morphologies of the nanocomposite laminates was discussed in detail.

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of nanocomposite laminate structure

The dependence of the longitudinal damping capacity of laminates on the testing temperature and frequency (Figure 2) shows that the incorporation of buckypapers into fiber laminates can improve longitudinal damping capacity due to rich interface and nanometer-size effect. Furthermore, the layer number and location of buckypapers strongly affect the longitudinal damping capacity of laminates. One piece of buckypaper located in the middle of laminates (C1) could be constrained fully by carbon fiber layers at both sides when subjected to the dynamic loading, exhibiting an optimal longitudinal damping capacity of the laminates. While two or more buckypapers were introduced into laminates, mutual coupling of constraint layers and CNT damping layers may decrease the damping capacity of laminates.

Figure 2 Longitudinal damping capacity of nanocomposite laminates

Based on the comparison of transversal damping capacity of nanocomposite laminates (Figure 3), it can be found that the number and location of buckypaper have little effect on the damping capacity of laminates. The main reason may be that the transversal modulus of CF unidirection laminates is generally too low to fully constrain the CNT damping layers under cyclic loading..

Figure 3 Transversal damping capacity of nanocomposite laminates

We can see from Figure 4 that the saturated water-absorption of laminates increases slightly with the number of buckypaper. The increment percent is less than 3 %, indicating that incorporation of buckypaper into CF laminates has little influence on moisture resistance.

Figure 4 Saturated water absorption of nanocomposite laminates

The ILSS results (Figure 5) show that incorporation of buckypapers somehow improves the shear strength of laminates under dry and wet states. It can be inferred that the ILSS of buckypaper reinforced composites is higher than that of CF laminates(C0), revealing satisfactory interfacial bonding of buckypaper and CF laminates.

Figure 5 Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of nanocomposite laminates

The fracture morphologies under shear loading (Figure 6) show that delamination damages occurred mainly in the interlaminar region of buckpaper and CF laminates. These observations also indicate the ILSS of buckpaper reinforced composites is higher than that of CF laminates, and the interfacial bonding strength for the CNT/CF laminates is comparable with that of CF laminates.

Figure 6 Fracture morphologies under shear loading of nanocomposite laminates

According to the above- mentioned results, it can be concluded the incorporation of buckypaper into laminates will produce positive effects on the damping capacity and mechanical properties of laminates.

Key words: Nanocomposite laminates; buckypapers; Damping factor, interlaminar shear strength (ILSS); Fracture morphologies